

Influence of Fibre Fineness on the Properties of Recycled Polyester Blended Yarns

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Abstract:

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of physical characteristics of recycled polyester (rPET)/modal and virgin polyester (vPET)/modal blended yarns produced using three different fibre finenesses with varying blends. A comparative assessment of rPET and vPET fibres revealed that rPET exhibited greater tenacity and breaking elongation. FTIR analysis confirmed the presence of identical functional groups in both polyesters. Thermal analysis indicated that rPET had slightly higher crystallinity, a faster crystallization rate, and lower transition temperatures than vPET. The results showed that yarns containing rPET were stronger, more extensible, and had increased hairiness, along with slightly higher imperfections compared to vPET yarns. Additionally, rPET-blended yarns displayed a higher unevenness percentage (U %) than those containing vPET.

Keywords: blend ratio, fibre fineness, modal fibre, recycled polyester, yarn characteristics

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1. Introduction

Synthetic polymers are prized for their lightweight nature, considerable strength, flexibility, and ease of use, rendering them suitable for a wide array of applications. Studies indicate that thermoplastic polymers such as polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), and polyester (PET) collectively account for roughly 80% of the world's polymer production. Among them, PET stands out, comprising approximately 18% of this total and ranking third in popularity, following PE and PP [1].

Polyester polymer found its earliest and most foundational application as a textile fibre following its discovery. Among all natural and manmade textile fibres, PET reigns supreme as the most widely utilized fibre about 54% of total fibre consumption [2]. Its prominence in this role is primarily due to the economic feasibility and widespread availability of raw materials, combined with its admirable functional properties.

PET, as a polymer, including textile fibres, finds extensive application across various sectors, like food containers, bottles for soft-drink and water, films, sheets, foams, industrial cords, electrical hardware and components, packaging materials, and more. Its widespread adoption is owed to its exceptional physical, mechanical, thermal, optical, and barrier properties [3, 4]. Additionally, PET stands out as an economical thermoplastic material, boasting excellent resistance to moisture and oxygen, good transparency, impressive tensile and impact strength, dimensional stability, and resistance to chemicals. Furthermore, it is non-toxic and do not have health hazards [5].

In industry, virgin PET polymer is manufactured to various specifications tailored to different applications, as each application demands specific properties. The required intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ for PET varies depending on its intended use, such as textile fibre (0.65 dl/g), recording film (0.60 dl/g), bottles (0.80 to 0.90 dl/g), and tyre cords (0.85 dl/g). PET granules can be processed in many ways such as extrusion, injection moulding and blow moulding, depending on application and the final product requirements [6-8].

In last few decades, PET bottles have surged in popularity due to their affordability, durability, resistance to microbes, and lightweight nature. Moreover, PET offers almost similar benefits to glass in terms of hygiene, taste

preservation, and gas impermeability. Consequently, PET bottles are increasingly replacing traditional glass bottles. Furthermore, PET bottle production is both cost-effective and energy-efficient, adding to their appeal [9].

In addition to above, the consumption of PET bottles tremendously rising due to technological advancements, economic growth of developing countries like India, along with increase in per capita demand and population growth. However, this trend leads to significant solid waste generation and contributes to landfill issues, as PET polymer biodegrades extremely slowly. These conditions could potentially aggravate ecological problems in the future [10, 11].

Recycling of PET waste bottles is the best way to economically reduce plastic waste [6, 12]. For recycling of PET plastic in many countries, it is coded "1" as the resin identification code and means high rate of recycling [14, 15]. Solid plastic waste is becoming a serious ecological and economic problem. Recycling or upcycling of used PET bottles into textile fibres offers a practical solution to these environmental challenges [13, 26]. This approach not only helps to conserve natural resources but also reduces energy consumption, lowering greenhouse gas emissions and carbon footprint. Furthermore, open new business opportunities and contribute in national economy. The first global effort to recycle waste PET bottles began in 1977 [16].

The recycling of PET bottles falls into two main categories: chemical recycling and mechanical recycling [17]. Chemical recycling involves breaking down used PET into monomers through total depolymerization or into oligomers through partial depolymerization, using processes like hydrolysis, methanolysis, and glycolysis. However, the major limitation of chemical recycling is that it incurs nearly the same production costs and energy consumption as producing virgin polyester [6]. In contrast, mechanical recycling is more cost-effective and consumes less energy, making it a more efficient method for upcycling the waste of PET bottles into textile fibres. Mechanical recycling primarily involves a melt extrusion process. It begins with the collection of PET bottles, followed by sorting and pre-washing. The bottles are then cut or shredded into flakes, and contaminants like caps, labels, and metals are separated through floatation. After washing and drying, the material undergoes melt extrusion for fibre production [18]. The success of PET bottles recycling process into fibre conversion greatly influenced by effectiveness of cleaning process in contamination removal and presence of water content at the time of remelting. Both factors are cause of reduction in molecular weight and intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ of the PET polymer. Innovative and cost-effective technologies for recycling PET bottles are boosting the PET recycling industry by offering increased value. This development is expected to provide the textile industry with more affordable recycled PET fibre, contrary this will also help in stabilising the price of virgin PET.

Various studies have been conducted in past to explore the utilization of recycled PET (rPET) in the production of fibres and yarns. In an investigation on the effects of structural and physical properties of both conventional and recycled PET polymers on spinning speed. Their findings indicate that, at spinning speeds ranging from 2500 to 3000 m/min, rPET filaments exhibit greater density and crystallinity compared to their virgin PET counterparts [19].

The effect of blend ratios on the quality characteristics of recycled polyester/cotton blended ring-spun yarns were studied and observe that the proportion of recycled polyester significantly influences the overall quality of these blended yarns [20]. The suitability of various yarn numbers and blend ratios for the application of rPET fibres that contributing to the understanding of optimal conditions for rPET usage was also examined [21]. The properties of yarns, produced from vPET, rPET, and cotton fibres, have been studied and observed that yarns made from recycled fibres exhibited superior yarn evenness, fewer imperfections, and a higher yarn quality index [22]. In one of the study researcher found that ring-spun yarns containing rPET fibres demonstrated lower tenacity and elongation compared to those made from virgin PET [23]. The antibacterial activities of 19.7 tex ring-spun yarns with varying blending ratios of lyocell and rPET were examined and authors concluded that lyocell/rPET blends were particularly suitable for hospital textiles due to their higher tenacity and elongation properties [24]. A study investigated the effects of recycling processes on the physical, mechanical, and degradation properties of PET yarns, revealing that virgin and chemically recycled yarns with adequate purification demonstrated comparable processability, physical and mechanical properties, and long-term degradation behaviour [25]. Another study on the properties of yarns made from rPET fibre blends with vPET fibres and cotton concluded that the desired performance of rPET yarns can be attained not by producing 100% pure rPET yarns but by blending them with other fibres [26].

However, the studies on blends of recycled PET fibres with modal fibre have not yet been conducted, particularly with a focus on various fibre finenesses. Previous research has indicated that recycled PET fibres exhibit lower tensile strength and other properties, likely due to inadequate recycling processes. However, advancements in recycling technologies have led to improvements in the quality and properties of recycled polyester fibres. Thus, it is essential to investigate the properties of recycled PET yarns made from fibres produced using these updated recycling methods.

This study aims to investigate and compare the effects of recycled PET (rPET) and virgin PET (vPET) fibres, with varying blend ratios and fibre fineness, on the properties of ring-spun yarn. Specifically, rPET and vPET fibres were blended with modal fibre in ratios of 100:0, 65:35, and 35:65, across three different levels of fibre fineness. Yarn samples were produced using a ring spinning system, with all production parameters held constant, to assess the impact of the blend ratio and fibre fineness variables.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Fibres Specifications

The recycled polyester (rPET), virgin polyester (vPET) & modal fibres were used in the present study. All fibres were provided by RSWM, Kharigram, Gulabpura. Both the fibres rPET & vPET were taken with three different fibre finenesses. The specifications and tensile properties of rPET & vPET and modal fibres are given Table 1.

Table 1: Specifications of rPET, vPET and modal fibres

Fibre	Fibre Fineness Denier (D)	Length (mm)	Tenacity (cN/tex)	Breaking Elongation (%)
rPET	1.2	44	61.89	17.69
	1.4	44	57.13	18.56
	2.0	44	54.21	20.07
vPET	1.2	44	55.76	17.05
	1.4	44	53.12	18.23
	2.0	44	50.27	19.78
Modal	1.2	38	26.54	8.32

2.2 Preparation of Yarn Samples

Ring yarns of rPET/Modal and vPET/Modal with a fineness of 19.5 tex were spun at RSWM, Kharigram, Gulabpura, utilizing three different blend ratios (100:0, 65:35, 35:65) and three fibre finenesses of 1.2 D, 1.4 D, and 2.0 D of both rPET and vPET fibres.

To blend rPET with Modal and vPET with Modal fibres, each of the two components underwent manual opening and thorough mixing to achieve a homogeneous blend. A predetermined quantity of manually blended fibres was then hand-fed to C-1/3 of LMW carding machine to prepare card sliver of 0.1hank. The conversion to drawn sliver was executed using an LMW draw frame DO-6, with two drawing passages given to the card sliver. The finisher sliver, obtained with a linear density of 0.1 hank, was then converted into 1.0 hank roving on Lakshmi Rieter's LF-1600. This roving was utilized to produce 19.6 tex yarn on Lakshmi Rieters' LR-5 ring frame, employing a spindle speed of 16,000 rpm.

All the yarns were tested for single strand strength, breaking extension, yarn irregularity, yarn imperfections and hairiness.

2.3 Fibre Test Results

To evaluate the chemical composition, molecular structure, thermal and tensile characteristics of rPET and vPET fibers, the test were performed utilizing Fourier Transform Infrared-Attenuated Total Reflection spectroscopy (FTIR-ATR), thermo-gravimetric analyser (TGA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and a tensile testing apparatus universal tensile machine (UTM).

FTIR-ATR tests were conducted on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer (M-2000) within 4000–500 cm^{-1} at 4 cm^{-1} resolution and 32 scans for each spectrum were taken and averaged and analyze the functional groups and polymer chain conformation in rPET and vPET fibers. From Figure 1, both polyesters showed similar FTIR spectra, with

an aromatic C-H bond peak at 745 cm⁻¹, a C=O (ester) double bond peak at 1780–1720 cm⁻¹, and a C-O-C (ester) single bond peak at 1290–1180 cm⁻¹. Thus, rPET and vPET fibers exhibit nearly identical functional groups.

Figure 1: ATR-FTIR spectrum of rPET (red) and vPET (black) fibres

The thermal stability of rPET and vPET fibers was evaluated using TGA and DTGA on a Perkin-Elmer Pyris 6 instrument. Samples (5 mg each) were heated from 30°C to 600°C at 10°C/min. Both fibres showed similar thermal degradation behaviour (Figure 2 and 3), with vPET having a slightly higher T_{onset} than rPET, as seen in the TGA thermograms. Both exhibited single-step degradation, with rPET experiencing greater weight loss, likely due to a higher fraction of short-chain molecules.

The DTGA curves (Figure 4) showed nearly overlapping T_{dmax} values, differing by only 0.5–0.1%/°C. The slightly higher DTGA peak intensity for vPET is attributed to longer chain lengths, while rPET displayed lower intensity. Both polyesters have comparable polydispersity, as indicated by the similar full width at half maximum of their DTGA peaks.

Figure 2: TGA curve of vPET and rPET Fibre

Figure 3: DTGA curve of vPET and rPET Fibre

Thermal properties, including melting temperature (T_m), glass transition temperature (T_g), crystallization temperature (T_c), and % crystallinity (χ_c), were analyzed using a Differential Scanning Calorimetry, DSC Q200 instrument. Samples were subjected to a heating cycle from 30–300°C (scan-a) and cooled back to 30°C (scan-b) at a rate of 10°C/min. Crystallinity (χ_c) was calculated using ΔH_m is the sample’s melting enthalpy and ΔH_m^o is the melting enthalpy of 100% crystalline PET (140 J/g) [27].

$$\chi_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_m^o} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots \text{eq. (1)}$$

As shown in Table 2 and Figure 4 (a) & (b), rPET exhibited slightly higher crystallinity, faster crystallization, and lower T_g , T_c , and T_m compared to vPET. The faster crystallization in rPET is attributed to its increased amorphous fraction, which aids crystalline lamella organization. The higher T_m of vPET (251 °C) versus rPET (246 °C) is likely due to its greater average molecular weight.

Table: 2 DSC Results for T_g , T_m , T_c , and Crystallinity (%) of rPET & vPET Fibres

Sample	T_g (°C)	T_m (°C)	Heat of Enthalpy (J/g)	T_c (°C)	Crystallinity (%) χ_c
rPET	94.6	246	40.49	211.3	28.57
vPET	95.3	251	38.51	215.9	27.50

Figure 4: DSC thermograms scan (a) for heating and scan (b) for cooling of vPET and rPET fibres

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Tenacity

To evaluate the tensile properties of the yarns, single strand strength and breaking extension tests were conducted using an Instron testing machine (Model 4411) in compliance with ASTM D2256. Gauge length of each yarn sample length was kept 500 mm, and the extension rate was set to ensure the specimen broke within a controlled time frame of 20 ± 2 seconds. For reliability of results 50 observations were taken and averaged.

Table 3 shows the results of the tensile test. The results show (Figure 5) that there are marked differences between the yarns spun with different fibre type, composition and fineness. Amongst all yarn combinations, both type of 100% polyester yarns, show maximum breaking strength, obviously it is due to higher strength of polyester than modal, Furthermore increase in modal content in blend composition results in lowering the resultant yarn strength because of modal fibre comparatively weaker than both type of polyester fibre. On analyzing the strength of rPET yarns with their vPET counter parts, the tenacity of rPET yarns is found to be significant higher; it may be due to higher value of crystallinity percentage and intrinsic viscosity fibres. While, on considering fibre fineness factor, it noticeably affects the yarn strength in all fibre blends. As the decrease in fibre diameter leads to improved breaking strength it is due to more frictional resistance provided by fine fibres against slippage and also because of higher tenacity of fine fibres.

Table 3: Influence of blend ratio and fibre fineness on Tenacity (cN/Tex) of rPET/Modal and vPET/Modal ring spun yarns

Fibre type	Fibre Fineness			
	Blend Ratio	F ₁ 1.2D	F ₂ 1.4D	F ₃ 2.0D
rPET/Modal	100/00	33.57	32.08	29.43
	65/35	26.85	26.07	24.16
	35/65	21.1	20.63	19.66
vPET/Modal	100/00	29.2	28.55	26.47

	65/35	24.32	23.71	21.84
	35/65	19.59	18.98	18.13

Figure 5: Influence of blend ratio and fibre fineness on Tenacity (cN/Text) of rPET/Modal and vPET/Modal ring spun yarns

3.2 Breaking Extension

As expected, in both types of rPET/Modal and vPET/Modal yarns an increase in modal content in the fibre mix results in decrease of breaking extension due to lower breaking extension of modal fibre. The maximum breaking extension is shown by 100% rPET yarns and followed by 100% vPET yarns and trend remain same for all fibre finenesses. Obviously, it is due to higher breaking extension of rPET fibres. For all fibre mix, the fineness of fibre also affects the breaking extension, as the denier of both types of polyester rises that leads to increase in breaking extension.

Table 4: Influence of blend ratio and fibre fineness on breaking extension (%) of rPET/Modal and vPET/Modal ring spun yarns

Fibre Type	Fibre Fineness			
	Blend Ratio	F ₁ 1.2D	F ₂ 1.4D	F ₃ 2.0D
rPET/Modal	100:0	12.41	12.89	13.56
	65:35	10.36	10.87	11.31
	35:65	8.29	8.76	9.31
vPET/Modal	100:0	12.08	12.74	13.31
	65:35	10.12	10.55	10.93
	35:65	8.07	8.59	8.98

Figure 6: Influence of blend ratio and fibre fineness on breaking extension of rPET/Modal and vPET/Modal ring spun yarns

3.3 Mass Irregularity

Yarn evenness, which reflects variations in thickness and mass, was analyzed using the Uster Evenness Tester (UT-III). Yarn test speed was kept for 50m/min for one minute and ten observation performed. The yarn irregularity (U%) of rPET and vPET containing both type of yarns ranges from 10.56% to 14.74% and 10.03% to 14.36%, respectively. In both types of fibre blends, an increase in fibre linear density leads to a significant rise in yarn unevenness. This is primarily due to the reduction in number of fibres in the yarn cross-section and due to increase in fibre denier. Additionally, as the modal content increases in all fibre compositions, there is a noticeable rise in mass irregularity. The reason can be attributed to comparatively high flexibility and lower smoothness of modal than polyester fibres; which tends to increase irregularity when blended with polyester fibres. However, when comparing the rPET yarns across various fibre blends to their vPET counterparts, the rPET yarns exhibit higher unevenness. This difference may be attributed to the variation in stiffness and linear density of rPET fibres compared to vPET fibres.

Table 5: Influence of blend ratio and fibre fineness on Mass Irregularity (U %) of rPET/Modal and vPET/Modal ring spun yarns

Fibre type	Fibre Fineness		F ₁	F ₂	F ₃
	Blend Ratio		1.2D	1.4D	2.0D
rPET/Modal	100/0		10.56	11.86	12.85
	65/35		11.65	12.79	13.81
	35/65		12.98	13.63	14.74
vPET/Modal	100/0		10.03	11.32	12.49
	65/35		11.21	12.32	13.47
	35/65		12.19	13.18	14.36

Figure 7: Influence of blend ratio and fibre fineness on Mass Irregularity of rPET/Modal and vPET/Modal ring spun yarns

3.4 Imperfections

From Table 6 and Figure 8, it is evident that for both rPET/modal and vPET/modal blended yarns, the number of imperfections increases as the modal content in the blend rises. This trend can likely be attributed to the higher probability of modal fibre breakage during the spinning process, resulting in the generation of short fibres. Furthermore, an increase in fibre denier is associated with a rise in the occurrence of thin and thick places in both fibre blends, which can be explained by a reduction in the number of fibres within the yarn cross-section. Conversely, a decrease in neps is observed with increasing fibre denier, likely due to the higher bending rigidity of coarser fibres.

When comparing yarns containing rPET to those containing vPET across all blend ratios and fibre fineness levels, rPET-containing yarns exhibit significantly higher imperfections. This difference can be attributed to the variations in stiffness and linear density between rPET and vPET fibres.

Table 6: Influence of blend ratio and fibre fineness on Total Imperfections/km of rPET/Modal and vPET/Modal ring spun yarns

Fibre type	Blend Ratio	Thin Places/km (-50%)			Thick Places/km (+50%)			Neps/km (+200%)			Total Imperfections/km		
		F1 1.2D	F2 1.4D	F3 2.0D	F1 1.2D	F2 1.4D	F3 2.0D	F1 1.2D	F2 1.4D	F3 2.0D	F1 1.2D	F2 1.4D	F3 2.0D
rPET/Modal	100/00	9	11	12	21	31	39	105	87	76	135	129	127
	65/35	11	14	16	29	38	43	131	116	101	171	168	160
	35/65	15	17	19	37	46	55	183	168	139	235	231	213
vPET/Modal	100/00	8	13	10	27	20	36	85	57	61	113	106	98
	65/35	10	12	16	31	34	40	118	93	71	159	139	127
	35/65	14	15	18	33	40	51	170	132	120	217	187	189

Figure 8: Influence of blend ratio and fibre fineness on Total Imperfections/km of rPET/Modal and vPET/Modal ring spun yarns

3.5 Hairiness

The hairiness results of the yarns are presented in Table 7 and Figure 9. The 100% rPET yarns exhibit the highest hairiness, while a significant reduction in hairiness is observed as the modal content increases in both types of fibre blends. Yarns containing finer fibres, show greater hairiness, attributed to the higher number of fibres in the yarn cross-section. However, rPET containing yarns have higher S_3 values compared to their vPET counterparts, which may be linked to the increased stiffness of rPET fibres, as indicated by their higher percentage crystallinity.

Table 7: Influence of blend ratio and fibre fineness on Hairiness (S_3) of rPET/Modal and vPET/Modal ring spun yarns

Fibre type	Fibre Fineness			
	Blend Ratio	F1 1.2D	F2 1.4D	F3 2.0D
rPET/Modal	100/0	536	449	346
	65/35	362	315	244
	35/65	291	242	218
vPET/Modal	100/0	513	423	329
	65/35	345	289	220
	35/65	279	221	197

Figure 9: Influence of blend ratio and fibre fineness on Hairiness (S_3) of rPET/Modal and vPET/Modal ring spun yarns

4. Conclusions

This study comprehensively compared the properties of recycled polyester (rPET) and virgin polyester (vPET) fibres and their impact on blended ring-spun yarns. Results showed that rPET exhibited higher tenacity and elongation at break than vPET, with nearly identical functional groups confirmed by FTIR. Thermal analysis indicated that rPET had slightly higher crystallinity, a faster crystallization rate, and lower transition temperatures (T_g , T_c , T_m) than vPET.

The tensile properties of rPET/modal and vPET/modal blended yarns were significantly influenced by fibre type, fineness, and blend ratio. 100% rPET yarns demonstrated higher tenacity than 100% vPET yarns despite exhibiting greater elongation at break. An increase in modal content in both fibre blends led to a reduction in tensile strength and elongation. Furthermore, as fibre denier increased in both rPET and vPET yarns, tenacity decreased while elongation at break improved.

Variations in fibre linear density affected yarn uniformity, with higher fibre denier leading to increased yarn unevenness. While the presence of thin and thick places increased with fibre denier, a reduction in neps was observed. Both rPET/modal and vPET/modal blended yarns exhibited greater yarn unevenness and total imperfections as modal content increased. Additionally, across different fibre blends, rPET yarns consistently displayed higher unevenness (U %) and significantly more imperfections than vPET yarns.

Hairiness measurements indicated that 100% rPET yarns had the highest hairiness, which decreased with greater modal content in both fibre blends. Finer fibres contributed to increased hairiness, while rPET yarns exhibited higher S_3 values compared to their vPET counterparts. These findings highlight the influence of fibre composition and structural properties on the overall quality and performance of rPET and vPET blended yarns.

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